

1 **PCLAF/Paf15 activation by HPV E2.**

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6 E2 has nuclear transcription activation related functions. We measured total transcription in human cells
7 following engineered expression of the human papillomavirus E2 gene for discovery for putative nuclear
8 factors associated with HPV E2 function. We report here activation of the PCNA clamp associated factor,
9 encoded by *Pclaf* (or Paf15) by human papillomavirus E2.

10 Citations

11 1. Chhetri, G., Badugu, S.B., Petriman, N.A., Petersen, M.B., Güller, A.S., Fajri, N., Coulée, M.,
12 Pitchai, G.P., Novotný, J., Larsen, F.T. and Møller, A.F., 2026. PAF15–PCNA exhaustion governs the
13 strand-specific control of DNA replication. *Nature*, pp.1-12.